

CONCEPTUAL ANALYSIS OF THE STATUE OF LIBERTY IN
AMERICAN LINGUO-CULTURE

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Annotation: Two notions, freedom and liberty has always been controversial topic in the field of linguo-conceptual study. Although they have similar meanings, several differential meanings can also be identified. The following article is going to analyse a number of idiosyncrasies by exempling “the Statue of Liberty” in American linguo-culture.

Key words: freedom, liberty, linguistic image, free will, freedom of speech, freedom from prosecution, pride, "Cleveland Gazette"

The concept of "freedom" is a concept rooted in both philosophical and everyday consciousness. The concept of freedom is broad, and it is usually associated with life, continuity, happiness, prosperity and success. The use of the concept of "freedom" can be explained by the fact that it refers to "a number of basic units of the image of the linguistic world, which are of existential importance both for a particular language individual and for a whole linguistic-cultural community." In American linguistic culture, two lexemes are used to express freedom: "freedom" and "liberty"

In the American linguistic culture, "freedom" is the main ideal and also the main value. For Americans, freedom has always been associated with freedom of personal choice and freedom of enterprise, unlimited faith in success and luck. This concept, which is considered in the minds of people, is presented in the form of the following lexemes: choice, life, peace, free will, liberty, freedom of speech, freedom from prosecution, pride.

According to etymological data, the name of the concept of "freedom" (freedom) goes back to the name of free, legal people. This interpretation of the word freedom is presented to us by Paul Auster in the novel "Leviathan": "It represents the concepts of democracy, freedom, equality under the law"¹

The symbol of liberty in American society is the well-known statue of the same name - the Statue of Liberty. It is a symbol of a developed, democratic state, occupies a special place in the value system of American society, and therefore plays an important role in shaping the worldview of Americans. Americans know that the concept of freedom is relevant not only for themselves, but also for other nations, and their task is to spread this ideal through cultural examples (books, films, other works of art). The concept of "Statue of Liberty" is a complex, multifaceted phenomenon saturated with philosophical content. It should be noted that this concept:

- unites Americans;
- based on individuality;
- has a rebellious force (because a person must inevitably fight for liberty and be ready to give his life).²

Historian David Glassberg, in his article "Rethinking the Statue of Liberty: Old Meanings, New Contexts", tries to reveal several meanings of the "Statue of Liberty" monument.³ The idea of creating the statue appeared in 1865, and in 1870, it was presented as a gift of the French people to America during the centenary of American independence. But the symbolic meaning of this gift is related to the unique political situation in France at the end of the 19th century. Walter Gray explained this in detail in his biography of Edouard Labouillet. Historian Barry Moreno calls Labouillet "the ideological father of sculpture."⁴ In the 1860s and 1870s, Labouillet and his circle in France fought to establish a liberal democratic republic against the absolute rule of

¹ Auster, P. Leviathan / Paul Auster. – London: Faber & Faber, 2005. – 245 p.

² Multiurok.ru. <https://multiurok.ru/files/kontsept-svoboda-v-amerikanskoi-ligvokulture.html>

³ David Glassberg, Rethinking the Statue of Liberty: Old Meanings, New Contexts. University of Massachusetts, Amherst, 2003. – p

3. <https://archives.iupui.edu/bitstream/handle/2450/678/RethinkingTheStatue-Glassberg.pdf>

⁴ Barry Moreno, The Statue of Liberty Encyclopedia (NY: Simon and Schuster, 2000), pp. 57.

Napoleon III on the one hand, and the revolutionary threat of the Paris Commune on the other.⁵ Among a number of scholars, art critics Albert Boime and Maurice Agul Khan noted that the strict image of the Statue of Liberty contradicts the revolutionary images of freedom that were prevalent earlier in the history of France. This led to the naming of the statue as "Statue de la Liberté" by the French, who supported moderate politics in response to the uprisings of the 1870s. The philosophical and symbolic meaning of the phrase is interpreted as "freedom leading the world to enlightenment".⁶

The sculpture project began in the 1870s and 1880s amid severe economic depression and labor unrest in the United States. In light of the 1886 Haymarket Rebellion in Chicago and radical Henry George's unsuccessful bid for mayor of New York, speakers at the statue's unveiling that same year cited it as evidence of the resilience of American political institutions.⁷ At the same time, the creators of the statue celebrated, on the one hand, the freedom provided by democratic political institutions under a constitutional government, and on the other hand, the end of slavery in America after the long civil war. In 1948, Herta Pauli and E. B. Ashton described the Statue of Liberty as the "Abolitionist Victory Column."⁸ Although scholars Pauley and Ashton noted that by 1948 this meaning had long since been lost, during the first fifty years of the statue's creation, the casualties of the Civil War had not yet faded from the memory of many Americans. At that time, some of them imagined that the chains of captivity were broken at the feet of the Statue of Liberty. For this reason, the Congress, which supported slavery at that time, criticized the statue, which the people consider to be a symbol of freedom.⁹ In addition, in the eyes of many African Americans, this monument is depicted as a symbol of the victory over slavery and the achievement of

⁵ David Glassberg, *Rethinking the Statue of Liberty: Old Meanings, New Contexts*. University of Massachusetts, Amherst, 2003. – p 3. <https://archives.iupui.edu/bitstream/handle/2450/678/RethinkingTheStatue-Glassberg.pdf>

⁶ David Glassberg, *Rethinking the Statue of Liberty: Old Meanings, New Contexts*. University of Massachusetts, Amherst, 2003. – p 3. <https://archives.iupui.edu/bitstream/handle/2450/678/RethinkingTheStatue-Glassberg.pdf>

⁷ Alan Trachtenberg, *The Incorporation of America; Culture and Society in the Gilded Age* (New York: Hill and Wang, 1982).

⁸ Herta Pauli and EB Ashton, *I Lift My Lamp: The Way of a Symbol* (New York: Appleton-Century-Crofts, 1948), p. 285

⁹ Jean Fagan Yellin, "Caps and Chains: Hiram Powers' Statue of 'Liberty'," *American Quarterly* 38 (Winter 1986): 798-826.

political freedom. About this, the following sentences could be seen in the "Cleveland Gazette", an American black publication:

"It is proper that the torch of the Bartholdi statue should not be lit until this country becomes a free one in reality. 'Liberty enlightening the world,' indeed!..."¹⁰

The reason why the monument was named with the lexeme of "liberty", which is a broader concept of "freedom", can be found from the inscription on the tableau held by the statue in its left hand. July 4, 1776 (the day of independence of the United States) was written on it.¹¹ After all, from this date, the Americans won the blessing of freedom that opened the way to many political freedoms.

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¹⁰ David Glassberg, Rethinking the Statue of Liberty: Old Meanings, New Contexts. University of Massachusetts, Amherst, 2003. – p 3. <https://archives.iupui.edu/bitstream/handle/2450/678/RethinkingTheStatue-Glassberg.pdf>

¹¹ uz.svayambhava.org. <https://uz.svayambhava.org/>

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